

Oxidation of olefins

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Abstract : Olefins on autoxidation form allyl hydroperoxides when C-H bonds are present at allyl position to the C=C double bond. Attack of oxygen on C=C double bond leads to the formation of oxiranes in different yields depending upon the structure of the starting olefin. Different mechanisms for the formation of allyl hydroperoxides, epoxides, mixed polyethers etc. have been taken into consideration. Influence of catalysts and selective oxidation have been discussed.

Keywords : Olefins, allyl hydroperoxides, epoxides, mixed polyethers, photooxidation.

The cyclohexene peroxide isolated¹ in the oxidation of cyclohex-1-ene was independently established²⁻⁴ as 3-hydroperoxy cyclohex-1-ene. The formation of the hydroperoxide was considered due to the autoxidation of the C-H bond at allyl position. A mixture of the corresponding hydroperoxides (five isomers are theoretically possible) in the autoxidation of 1-methylcyclohexene was obtained^{3,4}. Oxirane (epoxide) was obtained in smaller quantity along with the hydroperoxides which was not considered as a major oxidation product. In the oxidation of 1,2-dimethyl cyclohexene, allyl isomeric hydroperoxides along with the corresponding epoxide was obtained may be due to Priležev analogue reaction.

It is known well that such reaction mainly takes place only in the presence of Mo, V, or similar transition metal catalysts. Epoxide formed in the autoxidation of 2,4,4-trimethyl-pent-1-ene as a primary product of oxidation⁶. The formation of 4,4-dimethyl-pentan-2-one during the oxidation of 2,4,4-trimethyl-pent-1-ene must be considered due to the oxidative cleavage of the starting alkene. A free radical mechanism was formulated for the formation of the epoxide⁷. As a consequence of the oxidative cleavage of C=C double bond, formation of polymer peroxide, epoxide along with benzaldehyde and formaldehyde takes place⁸⁻¹¹. The nature of the reaction

products depends on the temperature and partial pressure of oxygen. The results in accordance to these assumptions were obtained in the oxidation of α -methylstyrene¹².

From the aforesaid results, one can draw the following conclusions :

- The attack of oxygen on active C-H bonds at allyl position to the C=C double bonds leads to the formation of allyl hydroperoxides.
- The attack of oxygen on C=C double bond gives the corresponding oxirane.
- Mixed oxygen containing polymers are formed by the reactions of oxygen and the starting alkene.

In view of the above conclusions, the formation of α -dicarbonyl compounds¹³⁻¹⁵ from the corresponding comparable acetylenes during the autoxidation can be explained. The mechanism of α -dicarbonyl compounds formation from the acetylenes is similar to earlier one¹⁰⁻¹².

Formation of allyl hydroperoxides :

The formation of allyl hydroperoxides can be understood on the basis of the autoxidation of alkanes and alkyl aromatics¹⁶.

Taking into account the fact that most of the alkenes possess different allyl positions, different allyl radicals formed lead to the formation of different allyl hydroperoxides which in turn decompose to give a variety of prod-

Formation of different allyl hydroperoxides

ucts. The allyl hydroperoxides are relatively stable and can be isolated in pure form but in lower yields in oxidation reactions carried out at temperatures lower than 100 °C.

Decomposition of hydroperoxides :

The hydroperoxides undergo decomposition during the oxidation as $\text{R-O-OH} \longrightarrow \text{RO}\cdot + \cdot\text{OH}$. The decomposition is responsible for the self acceleration of the reaction.

The questions that arise now are : (a) How is the structure of the starting alkene influence the composition of the reaction products ? (b) How can the product composition be influenced by changing the conditions such as temperature, partial pressure of oxygen, concentration of the starting alkene and using catalysts ?

The allyl alcohols and α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds are formed partly through the decomposition of the corresponding hydroperoxide¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and partly through chain termination between secondary and or primary peroxy radicals.

Chain initiation :

Chain propagation :

Chain branching :

Chain termination :

The termination between two secondary or primary peroxy radicals takes place by Russell mechanism²⁰⁻²³ over the alkyl tetroxide giving a molecule of carbonyl compound, a molecule of alcohol and a molecule of singlet oxygen^{24,25}.

The data set of constitutional and topological descriptors for a QSPR study show OH radical addition²⁶ to the

unsaturated hydrocarbons as the dominant reaction pathway. The formation of ketones and alcohols by the decompositions of secondary hydroperoxides can be represented as follows :

Chain initiation :

Formation of ketones :

Formation of alcohols :

Decomposition of secondary hydroperoxides

Selective manufacture of alcohols and ketones from alkenes by oxidation process using molecular oxygen different from the classical Wacker oxidation as they do not involve any redox-coreductants catalysed by transition metal compounds²⁷ is well-known.

Formation of epoxide :

The formation of epoxide (oxirane) from alkenes in autoxidation can be formulated as shown below⁷.

Addition of peroxy radical to alkene leads to the formation of allyl radical. Allyl peroxy radical formed with

Formation of epoxide

The free radical epoxidation of *cis* or *trans* alkene is not stereospecific²⁸⁻³¹

the interaction of oxygen add to the starting alkene to give peroxyalkyl radical. The decomposition of the peroxide bond of the peroxyalkyl radical results in the formation of oxirane (epoxide) and an alkoxy radical. The alkoxy radical so formed can attack the starting alkene to give α,β -unsaturated alcohol and the allyl radical. The life period of the peroxyalkyl radical formed by the addition of peroxy radical to the starting alkene is sufficiently high and therefore the radical can change the conformation due to the free rotation of the C-C single bond formed by the π -bond cleavage.

The reaction of acylperoxy radicals with alkenes is mainly responsible for the epoxide formation and these reactions take place at higher velocities than those between allylperoxy radicals and alkenes^{13,32-35}. It is obvious that the addition of acylperoxy radicals on the double bond is in concurrence with the abstraction of H-atoms of C-H bonds at allyl position^{33,34,36}. Naturally, the epoxidation with acylperoxy radicals is also not stereospecific³⁷. The fact that the amount of the oxidation products formed through oxidative cleavage of C=C double bond argues against the Emanuel's formulations.

The olefins having no C-H bonds at allyl position e.g. styrene, norbornene derivatives and bicyclo[2.2.2]octane gave high yields of epoxides while olefins with C-H bonds at allyl positions e.g. α,β -methylstyrene and 2,4,4-trimethyl-pent-1-ene form besides the epoxides and products of the oxidative cleavage of C=C double bond, lower yields of the allyl oxidation products. The stoichiometry of the products of the oxidation can't be explained by Twigg's mechanism.

Now the question to be looked after is to explain the formation of epoxide in high yields of 60-70% in the oxidation of norbornene derivatives along with 30-40% polymer peroxides and traces of acids. The argument that oxidation of aldehydes formed during the oxidation leads to acylperoxy radicals which can also epoxidise the alkene^{28,29} can not be considered in this case as no aldehydes can form³⁸⁻⁴⁰. A modification of Twigg's mechanism has been given to explain the higher yields of norbornene derivatives. Two molecules of the alkene react with a molecule of oxygen to deliver two molecules of epoxide.

Oxidative cleavage of C=C double bond :

The formation of 4,4-dimethylpentan-2-one in considerable amounts besides epoxide in the autoxidation of 2,4,4-trimethylpent-1-ene⁶ should be considered as a cleavage product of the C=C double bond. Mayo concluded that the oxidative cleavage of C=C double bond is precedence before the formation of the epoxide in the oxidation of styrene^{9,10} and α,β -methylstyrene¹¹. Mayo formulated a mechanism to explain the formation of the epoxide, the oxidative cleavage products and mixed polymer peroxides.

Peroxy and alkoxy radicals can act as chain propagation radicals. The peroxyalkyl radical formed by the addition of a peroxy radical to the alkene double bond decomposes to give an alkoxide and the corresponding epoxide via the Twigg's mechanism or it can react with oxygen to give peroxyalkylperoxy radical which in turn adds to a molecule of the starting alkene to form a peroxyalkyl radical with two peroxide functions which

Formation of epoxide of *exo*-norbornene nitrile

Mayo mechanism - cleavage of C=C double bond and formation of polymer peroxide

undergoes decomposition to give the epoxide and a peroxyalkoxy radical which undergoes a simultaneous cleavage of the C-C bond between the two oxygen functions and the peroxide O-O bond resulting in the formation of an alkoxy radical and two carbonyl compounds. The Mayo mechanism of the oxidative cleavage of the C=C double bond points to the dependence of the ratio of the epoxide and the cleavage products upon the partial pressure of oxygen. The Mayo mechanism has been supported by the findings :

(a) Peroxyalkylhydroperoxide considered as a consecutive product of peroxyalkylperoxy radical was isolated in the autoxidation of cycloalkenes⁴¹.

(b) The fact that the thermolysis and photolysis of styrene peroxide gave benzaldehyde and formaldehyde which are the consecutive products of the C=C double bond cleavage is in agreement with the formation of peroxyalkoxy radical by the thermal decomposition of the mixed polymers formed from styrene and oxygen which undergo fragmentation leading to the formation of the C=C double bond cleavage products⁴².

The peroxy radicals can attack the allyl C-H bonds

and also the double bond. The attack at allyl C-H bonds leads to the formation of allylhydroperoxides, allyl alcohols and α,β -unsaturated compounds. The attack on C=C double bond leads to the formation of oxirane, polymer peroxides and also the lower carbonyl compounds due to oxidative cleavage. If all peroxy radicals attack on C=C double bond and all alkoxy radicals at allyl C-H bonds, one should expect to obtain a maximum of 50% yield of oxirane besides 50% allyl alcohol formation. Higher epoxide formation i.e. >50% can't be explained either by Twigg's or Mayo's mechanism. It should not be considered that the alkoxy and respectively allyl oxyradicals formed attack totally C-H bonds at allyl position. They can also naturally react with C=C double bond of the starting hydrocarbon so as to form the ether bonds. In the case of styrene, or norbornene or from other olefins where there is no reactive C-H bond at allyl position, polyethers must have formed by this way.

Emanuel *et al.* formulated the oxidative cleavage through the four ring dioxetene to explain the lower and higher yields of acetic acid and formic acid respectively and the lower concentrations of allyl oxidation products in the reaction mixture of the oxidation of propene⁴³.

The same mechanism was formulated in the autoxidation of non-1-ene⁴⁴. The fact that the C=C double bond cleavage products are also formed from such alkenes which do not have C-H bonds at allyl position and the observations that only those carbonyl compounds are formed which are expected by the Mayo mechanism argues against Emanuel's mechanism.

Cernjak⁴⁵ formulated the oxidative cleavage through 1,2-dioxetane although its formation from alkene and triplet oxygen is in reality a symmetry prohibited synchronic reaction.

The formation of 1,2-dioxetane through a step-wise diradical reaction is imaginable in principle. The possibility of dioxetane formation in thermal alkene oxidation has been formulated by Bljumberg *et al.* in the oxidation of norbornene nitrile, styrene and 2,3-dimethylbut-2-ene on the basis of the chemiluminescence⁴⁶ observed. It is to be proved whether the luminescence is due to the dioxetane or due to the rash decomposition of the oligomer and polymer peroxides.

Formation of dioxetane - analogue to Bljumberg mechanism of epoxide formation

Mix polymerization with oxygen :

From the Mayo mechanism, it is clear that the mix polymers or oligomers can form from alkene and oxygen. When the peroxyalkyl radical with two peroxide functions doesn't undergo fragmentation but reacts further with oxygen and the starting olefin successively, polymer peroxides are formed. Each individual step of the polymerization leads to the possibility of the fragmenta-

tion of the peroxyalkyl radical. Presumably, the steric suppositions for the fragmentation in increasing degree of polymerization are always difficult to set up so that mix polymers of higher mass⁴⁷ can form. It must be proved that mix polymerization with oxygen is possible with those alkenes which can undergo radical homopolymerisation easily and that these alkenes give mixpolymers as the main product⁴⁸ only at temperatures below 50 °C. At higher temperatures ~ 100 °C, the epoxide and the oxidative cleavage products of C=C double bond are formed.

Formation of polyethers :

In Mayo's mechanism, an alkoxy radical is formed per molecule of oxirane. The alkoxy radical propagates the chain reaction in which it can react with a C-H bond at allyl position or attach to the C=C double bond of the starting alkene. The reaction with a C-H bond at allyl position offers no speciality as it leads to the formation of an allyl radical and a molecule of allyl alcohol. By the addition to the C=C double bond, an alkoxyalkyl radical is formed. Alkoxyalkyl peroxy radical formed from alkoxyalkyl radical with oxygen effects again epoxidation, thus forming an alkoxy radical which leads to the formation of oligomer and polymer glycol ethers. In the case of alkenes having no active C-H bonds at allyl position e.g. styrene, norbornene etc., as a consequence of Mayo formulations, one expects to obtain the oligomer or polymer glycol ethers containing a mole of the starting alkene per mole of the epoxide formed. Oligomer glycol ethers can also form under the conditions of the oxidation from the oxirane formed. The epoxide ring opening can be catalysed by the presence of carboxylic acids in the oxidation mixtures. Surprisingly most of the epoxides formed are stable towards carboxylic acids. Polyglycol ethers are expected along with polyperoxides in the residue products of all alkene oxidations. One has to find out the methods to examine the residue products.

Influence of catalysts and selectivity :

The question of special interest is whether the catalysts influence the ratio of epoxide formation and allyl oxidation so that the selectivity of the olefin oxidation can be increased. It is expected that the oxygen attached to the complex⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ possess radical character and therefore should cause epoxidation in an analogue to Twigg's mechanism but no increase in the yields of epoxides was observed.

Hydrogen peroxide is probably the best terminal oxidant^{52,53} after dioxygen with respect to environmental and economic consideration. Sometimes, it is better than oxygen as O₂-organic mixtures can sometimes spontaneously ignite. Epoxidation systems that use H₂O₂ in conjunction with catalytic amounts of cheap, relatively non-toxic metals and their derivatives⁵⁴ are potentially viable for specialized applications. It has been observed that the homolytic cleavage generates free radicals in solution leading to spurious reactions that can degrade the catalyst and unproductive consumption of the substrate and product. Heterolytic activation of hydrogen peroxide whereby the O-O bond is cleaved heterolytically without radical production may be of great importance.

Homolytic cleavage of hydrogen peroxide O-O bond :

This mechanism leads to Fenton-type chemistry.

Heterolytic cleavage of hydrogen peroxide O-O bond :

This mechanism can lead to clean oxygen transfer.

There is no single method for epoxidations using hydrogen peroxide that is uniformly better than the rest. The best method available depends on desired substrate and reaction scale. Zeolites⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ were found suitable and better for the production of small and stable epoxides. Clean selective reactions were observed with rhenium system⁵⁸⁻⁶¹.

The epoxidation of alkenes using molecular oxygen via a catalytic process is a challenging subject in the field of oxidation chemistry⁶². Since the direct epoxidation of alkenes with molecular oxygen, which lies in triplet ground state, is inhibited, epoxidation using O₂ is carried out in the presence of a compound like an aldehyde which serves as an active oxygen carrier. Although there have been many reports on the metal catalyzed epoxidation of alkenes by O₂ in the presence of aldehydes, only a limited number of methods using O₂ as terminal oxidant have been developed^{63,64}. There has been long standing interest in the epoxidation of alkenes with alkylhydroperoxides formed from the starting hydrocarbons and oxygen as an active oxygen carrier.

A major difficulty in the epoxidation is attributed to :

(i) Autoxidation of aldehydes takes place at least two orders of magnitude faster than that of hydrocarbons.

(ii) As a result, the epoxidation using hydrocarbons must be carried out under severe reaction conditions.

(iii) The epoxidation ability of alkyl hydroperoxides is considerably lower than that of peracids or acylperoxy radicals derived from aldehydes and O₂. Therefore, stepwise procedures are commonly utilized in epoxidations using alkyl hydroperoxides. For example, the Halcon process consists of the aerobic oxidation of ethylbenzene to α -hydroperoxy ethylbenzene. An epoxidation could be induced even at room temperature to afford epoxide in high selectivity (97%) at 31% conversion⁶⁵. Metal complexes e.g. MoO₂(acac)₂, VO(acac)₂ and TiO(acac)₂ were found to be inadequate for the reaction. The hydrocarbons were efficiently oxidized with O₂ by NHPI (N-hydroxyphthalimide) which serves as a radical catalyst under mild conditions. The hydrocarbons are converted into oxygen-containing compounds such as alcohols or ketones through alkyl hydroperoxides as transient intermediates. Molybdenum catalyzed epoxidation of alkenes with hydroperoxides generated *in situ* by the NHPE-catalyzed aerobic oxidation of hydrocarbons has been formulated as follows

The epoxidation of *cis*-olefins was shown to proceed with nearly complete stereoselectivity to give *cis*-epoxide, although the metal catalyzed epoxidation of *cis*-olefins using an aldehyde and oxygen leads to a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-epoxide⁶⁶.

Much attention has been focused on selective oxygenation of the C=C double bond moiety by molecular oxygen⁶⁷. Of these cobalt complex-catalyzed autoxidation in the presence of a hydrogen donor such as 2-propanol, hydrogen peroxide, or BH₄⁻ seems to be unique, since products are alcohols and ketones instead of allylic alcohols and epoxides as expected in the conventional autoxidation reactions^{68,69}.

A novel peroxidation reaction of alkenes catalyzed by

bis-(1,3-diketonato)cobalt(II) in the presence of Et_3SiH has been reported. A variety of biologically active cyclic peroxides such as analogues of Yingzhaosu C⁷², Yingzhaosu A⁷³ and Artemisiniu⁷⁴ were prepared from alkenes via corresponding hydroperoxides. The characteristic behaviour of the Co^{III} -cumylperoxy complex in the presence of Et_3SiH ⁷⁵ is in marked contrast to the fact that, in the absence of Et_3SiH , the complex catalyzes autoxidation of alkenes to provide products such as allylic alcohols and α,β -unsaturated ketones^{76,77}. It has been well established that under the latter conditions, homolytic fission of the O-O bond or the Co-O bond yielding an alkoxy radical or an alkylperoxy radical is the predominant mode of decomposition of the Co^{III} -alkylperoxy complex. It is well known that under an oxygen atmosphere, Co^{III} -alkyl complex transforms into the corresponding Co^{III} -alkyl peroxy complex⁷⁸ by homolytic cleavage of the C-Co bond and subsequent trap by molecular oxygen.

Terminal alkenes nearly always give methyl ketones suggesting that hydroxyl palladation takes place according to Markownikov's principles, while disubstituted alkenes give products that do not always obey these rules⁷⁹. Dramatically different regioselectivity was observed with styrene (Markownikov) and that of β -methylstyrene (anti-Markownikov)⁸⁰. The allylic hydrogen was found responsible for the change in regioselectivity of the Wacker oxidation. Removal of the allylic hydrogen switched the regioselectivity back to the Markownikov product. It was also observed that the steric environment does not have an overriding influence on the regioselectivity⁸¹ of the Wacker oxidation.

Highly selective epoxidation⁸² of pent-1-ene with H_2O_2 over TS-1⁸³, a titanium containing silicate with MFI structure with no side-reactions should be considered as a desired and forward step.

Oxidation of non-1-ene and styrene in the presence of ruthenium complexes showed an increase in epoxide yields⁸⁴. Rhodium complexes influenced the formation of methyl ketones^{85,86}.

The Halcon activated compounds catalyse the reaction between the alkyl hydroperoxides formed with the starting olefin⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹.

It is interesting to note that about 90% hydroperoxide could be obtained from cyclohexene without catalysts while in the presence of Mo-catalysts⁹⁰ only 40 to 50% epoxide was achieved. Reaction of peracids⁹¹ with olefins and Baeyer and Villiger formation of peracids in the oxidation of aldehydes⁹² were employed together⁹³ to obtain 20-80% epoxide. Epoxide formation in cooxidation of propylene with aldehydes is not due to Preleřaev reaction⁴³. The acyl peroxy radicals formed as intermediates in the aldehyde oxidation mediate the oxidation of the olefin as Twigg's-mechanism.

Dioxiranes^{94,95} offer a powerful and often ability to transfer an oxygen atom to a wide variety of substrates including carbon-carbon double bonds, carbon-hydrogen bonds in hydrocarbons etc. Adam and Smerz⁹⁶ have documented substituent and solvent effects in regio and diastereoselective epoxidation of allyl alcohols by DMDO.

The density functional theory B3LYP/6-31G* provides a detailed understanding of the origins of intra- and intermolecular effects⁹⁷ on the epoxidation of C-C double bonds.

Dioxiranes generated *in situ* from chiral ketones have been shown to be effective reagents for asymmetric epoxidation^{98,99} of alkenes. Prochiral olefins show that the epoxidation catalysed by the ketone proceeds through spiro transition state^{100,101}.

Asymmetric epoxidation¹⁰² has led to the synthesis of enantioselective compounds of biological importance. Chiral catalyst molecules leading to the synthesis of chiral product molecules¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁷ has brought a revolution in the

fields of medicine and pharmaceuticals. The problems like recovery and recycling of the catalyst systems in homogeneous catalytic methods can be overcome in heterogeneous catalytic systems. High enantioselectivity¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹² could be attained in asymmetric epoxidation. Polymer supported catalyst systems¹¹³⁻¹¹⁵ for enantioselective and asymmetric processes for epoxidation are well known. Asymmetric epoxidation of aliphatic terminal olefins by polymer supported amino acid Cu^{II} 116 complexes at 25-40 °C with high selectivity was reported. Metal complex catalysis and its application¹¹⁷ for oxyfunctionalization of various olefins including the naturally occurring ones via selective oxidation must be viewed as an important step towards fine chemistry.

Photooxidation of cyclopropenes¹¹⁸ free radical mechanism and the reaction products in terms of secondary rearrangements of the hydroperoxide and epoxide were formulated as

Surprisingly, no ¹O₂ reaction¹¹⁹⁻¹²¹ is observed. Dioxetene formation from olefins by the mechanism¹²² of (2+2) cycloaddition of ¹O₂ is not still crystal clear.

Intrazeolite photooxidations of electron-poor alkenes show divergent behaviour¹²³. Intrazeolite singlet oxygen ene reactions exhibiting a unique regioselectivity for hydrogen abstraction from the least substituted side and the most substituted end of trialkyl-substituted alkenes¹²⁴ were also formulated.

Conclusion :

A large number of research publications dealing with high selectivity of asymmetric, enantioselective and chemoselective epoxidation have appeared. Still there exists a tremendous scope and need for the development of the methods where both oxygen atoms of the dioxigen can be transferred as it leads to green or clean chemistry and development of recyclable catalysts including the chiral ones which can be used under ambient conditions.

Photooxidation of cyclopropene

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